

Research Paper

Preliminary results of extensive tractor rollover stability tests using a tilting-rotating rig

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ABSTRACT

Addressing safety issues in mountain agro-forestry operations, a critical focus is on the stability of machines to prevent rollovers. Despite advancements in technologies and techniques enhancing overall safety, fatalities remain a significant concern. Italy, for instance, witnesses over 120 fatal accidents annually due to tractor rollovers. Even in less serious cases, they still lead to considerable vehicle damage and financial losses. Consequently, investigating and characterising the tractor stability behaviour emerges as a crucial endeavour. This has led to consider in this work, also for certification purposes, the definition of mixed approaches typical of twin models, with predictive modelling assessments extended to a broad application context complemented by punctual measurements on full-scale machines. These measurements have been carried out by means of a novel rotating and tilting test-rig for tractor rollover evaluation available at the Agroforestry Innovation Laboratory (AFILab) of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. The study concentrates in particular on examining and comparing the (static) rollover stability results on three different types of tractors commonly employed in mountain operations: a conventional tractor, a narrow track tractor, and a mountain-specialist model. The output of this approach are the stability maps, graphical tools summarising stability limit conditions for diverse configurations. The preliminary results, despite some simplifications adopted in the first version of the digital model, show an excellent correlation between the modelling approach and real measurements. Aspects for future refinement may concern the inclusion of procedures capable of reproducing tyre deformation with greater fidelity under conditions of significant slope.

1. Introduction

The persistent problem of vehicle rollovers, particularly of off-road machines such as agricultural and earth-moving machines, continues to pose serious threats to drivers' safety, with often fatal consequences. In Italy, that after USA and Japan is on third place in the working tractor ranking (i.e. about 1.75 million units) (Facchinetti et al., 2021), the number of fatalities in agriculture recorded by the National Institute for Insurance Against Accidents at Work (INAIL) (INAIL. Banca Dati Statistica., n.d.) was 735 in the quinquennium spanning 2018–2022. A predominant cause of incidents was identified during machinery operation (almost 22 %), notably tractor usage, with a high incidence of overturning incidents (i.e. about half out of total tractor fatalities (Felaco et al., 2023)). An average of approximately 118 rollover fatalities per year are reported in Italy over the period 2008–2019, unfortunately without any decrease trend. This despite, over the years,

legislative and manufacturing efforts to establish clear test guidelines and to enhance safety measures have been made, as well as the spreading a safety culture among operators (Facchinetti et al., 2021). Even in less severe cases, where operators escape unharmed or with minor injuries, substantial damage to vehicles and loss of income due to work interruption are significant implications (Bietresato & Mazzetto, 2020). In any case, these statistics are not always up to date: many incidents are not officially recorded, or at least not reported correctly and completely. A study conducted in Spain (Arana et al., 2010) revealed that only the 61.9 % of the records were consistent. In addition, official statistics often consider only accidents involving professional workers, but many non-professional figures who exploit the tractor in their free time should be also considered. With this in mind, some studies (Facchinetti et al., 2021) propose dedicated observatory systems that examine news and information web portals, whereas others (Moreschi et al., 2017) define new methodology to precisely reconstruct the

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dynamics of the accident (i.e. through an integrated analysis of the death scene, vehicle, traumatic lesions and their comparison with the mechanical structures of the tractor and the morphology of the terrain). Statistics also report that almost half of the victims were usually between 61 and 80 years old (Facchinetti et al., 2021). This is because this category generally uses old and worn tractors, often not equipped with ROPS and seat belts. For the Italian situation, a detailed analysis of the different accident causes is well documented in Rovelli et al. (2018). A large percentage of fatal accidents caused by overturning tractors (71.7 %) refers to non-ROPS equipped vehicles. This on the one hand demonstrates the effectiveness of these safety devices, the installation of which is mandatory on new machines. Indeed, a ROPS, if used correctly together with a seat belt, is 99 % effective in preventing injury or death in the event of a rollover (Murphy et al., 2010). On the other hand, however, it shows that even if ROPS devices are regularly present, they are often (26.5 % of accidents) either removed or left in the folded position. In any case, given that older tractors with inadequate safety technology components represent a large percentage of the circulating fleet (in Italy 40 % of tractors are over 30 years old) many studies suggest and promote the retrofitting of ROPS solutions even on these older machines (Fagnoli & Lombardi, 2020; Vita et al., 2021).

In this context, the development of digital twin approaches through models that predict the stability behaviour of a machine operating on a slope, combined with full-scale experimental tests in controlled environments, becomes of primary importance. Digital twins, as is well known, are tools based on increasingly complex modelling methodologies that simulate the behaviour of specific entities in their real-life contexts, in order to make better, targeted decisions on their management mode. The most widespread applications of digital twins include, precisely, real-time monitoring and control functions on complex systems, in order to intervene on the responsiveness and management of processes (Fuller et al., 2020). In the case at hand, this helps either the design of new machines with more reliable passive safety systems, or systems that can be retrofitted to older machines, or even active systems for overturning prevention, such as a rollover warning device (Carabin et al., 2016), a steering inhibition systems in case it leads to instability (He et al., 2023; Qin et al., 2019), automatic blocking of the joint of the pivoting axle, etc. As described in the exhaustive review of Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2024), the problem of stability is addressed by means of three types of models.

- (1) kinematic models, which study the phenomenon by considering purely geometric parameters (e.g. CoG position and machine dimensions) and kinematic relationships among the tractor main body parts. This approach is considered for instance in the works of Smith et al. (1974), Guzzomi (2012), Mazzetto et al. (2013) and Franceschetti et al. (2021).
- (2) (quasi)-static models, based on the calculation of a force mechanical equilibrium that can also take account of tyre deformability. In this case the dynamic contributions are neglected in order to simplify the analysis. This is equivalent to assuming that the tractor is moving at low speed and that the slope changes gradually. Work based on this analysis have been done by Previati et al. (2014) and Baker and Guzzomi (2013). If the effects of higher operating speeds and the dynamics of interaction with obstacles are also to be considered in the simulations,
- (3) dynamic models have to be considered. More complex to be implemented and requiring more computational efforts, they are able to describe the stability behaviour more accurately as in the work of Li et al. (2015) and He et al. (2023). Dynamic models also enable the study of more complex interactions with the terrain that may directly or indirectly lead to rollover. For example, terrain roughness can cause tractor bouncing, potentially resulting in understeer and subsequent overturning (Watanabe & Sakai, 2020). The influence of terrain, particularly the surface roughness, has also been investigated in Li et al. (2018) using a

scale-model-based experimental approach. The authors focus on the terrain roughness influence on various techniques aimed at improving stability (e.g., front ballast, rear track width). As a result of these analyses, the stability behaviour of the machine is often represented by stability indices. Examples are the Lateral-load Transfer Ratio (Li et al., 2016) based on the load transfer ratio, or the Tractor Stability Index (Ahmadi, 2011) that evaluates the CoG height.

What these indices often have in common, however, is their assessment of the machine lateral stability alone. This, although being the most critical condition, is not the only condition in which a rollover can occur. There are also more complex and comprehensive studies that consider the stability of a tractor in various orientations and conditions (Bietresato & Mazzetto, 2020; Carabin et al., 2016; Previati et al., 2014; Vidoni et al., 2015). In this case, instead of using an index, the stability is described by means of graphs (i.e. Cartesian or polar) which identify the limiting angle for each orientation of the machine. Among the various applications of the Digital Twin approach is the development of realistic driving simulators. In recent years, these have become valuable tools not only for studying the causes of accidents but, above all, for driver training (Wang et al., 2024). These systems feature tractor and environment virtual models, with varying degrees of realism, along with a range of device that enable the reciprocal interaction between operator and simulator (e.g., controls, screens, motion platforms, etc.) to create an immersive and realistic experience (Ojados Gonzalez et al., 2017).

Whereas simulations are an important tool for quickly testing a multitude of configurations and situations that are difficult to achieve (i.e. due to lack of time, high costs and safety concerns), experimental tests on full-scale machines are necessary to validate the mathematical models and tune them. Currently, the test equipment used in machine type-approval centres, such as the OECD test centres, and related test procedures with standard equipment, only cover pure static lateral or longitudinal rollover scenarios (Bietresato & Mazzetto, 2019). Although these configurations offer the advantage of using common equipment (e.g. tilting test-bench), they represent only two specific conditions in which a vehicle may find itself. This is reflected also in many papers in the literature, generally limited to the lateral rollover stability investigations (Baker & Guzzomi, 2013; Majdan et al., 2021; Pessina et al., 2022). Typically, these studies focus on specific tractor/platform configurations, e.g. tracked, 4-wheel, rigid or articulated body, etc. Only few exceptions, such as Pessina et al. (2022), consider further (limited) tractor orientations other than just lateral rollover. Some authors (Franceschetti et al., 2014; Guzzomi, 2012; Guzzomi et al., 2009; Simion & Nastase, 2009) have explored also dynamic stability behaviour of tractors. However, these tests are not standardised, and their experiments involve significant safety issues associated with the need for a driver on board to perform them safely. Or in any case, even if a remote-control system is used, given their destructive nature, these tests have high running costs and, above all, repeatability problems. Therefore, from an experimental perspective, these studies are often approached using scale testing platforms. Examples are the works of Jang et al. (2022); Li et al. (2014) that analyse the influence on stability of obstacles on the terrain, or of particular terrain conformations (e.g. presence of ditches, variable slope ramps, etc.).

In light of this, it was decided to install an innovative system at the Agroforestry Innovation Laboratory (AFILab) of the Free University of Bolzano, Italy, to test the machines stability in different orientations, configurations and conditions. Developed in conjunction with De Pretto Industrie s.r.l. (Schio - VI, Italy), the initial concept (Fig. 1a) involved a platform with two adjustable plates designed for dynamic testing with moving vehicles (Bietresato & Mazzetto, 2022). However, due to the complexity and safety issues associated with dynamic tests requiring the presence of a driver, the design was later refined. Thus, the original design firstly evolved into a scaled-down version with a single plate capable of adjusting the tilt angle with respect to the ground. In this

Fig. 1. From (a)–(c): conceptual evolution of the design of the stability test installation.

configuration, only a circular section of the plate could rotate in order to orient the tractor, effectively simulating static tilting conditions (Fig. 1b). Finally, further simplification led to the development of a turntable equipped with four individual plates (Fig. 1c), providing the flexibility to adjust vertical levels for each plate. This iterative refinement process culminated in the current sophisticated turntable model, which offers greater adaptability and a controlled test environment for comprehensive static evaluations.

The main objective of this work is therefore to evaluate and validate the feasibility of conducting experimental tilting tests with different machine orientations, using the developed test rig. A simplified rollover stability model is then presented, capable of determining the limiting (static) stability angles for each machine configuration. These values are then compared with those determined experimentally to validate the model.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Stability test-rig

The stability test-rig, visible in Fig. 2a, comprises a versatile platform with the capability to tilt (α angle in Fig. 3) and position (β angle in Fig. 3) the tractor under test in any orientation. The system consists of a

Fig. 3. Definition of tilting angle α and orientation angle β .

base situated within a recessed pit, affording accessibility at street level through a lateral ramp (Fig. 2c). Integrated into the base, a tilting mechanism (Fig. 2b) is used to incline the upper platform up to an angle

Fig. 2. (a) Stability test-rig, (b) tilting mechanism and fifth-wheel coupling, (c) access ramp and platform plates, (d) plates vertical shifting mechanism, (e) tractor anchoring with chains, (f) plate metal grid.

Fig. 4. Tested tractors: (a) New Holland TN75-V, (b) New Holland T6.17 and (c) Reform Metrac H75.

Fig. 5. (a) Straight direction, (b) left and (c) right conventional steering, (d) left and (e) right four wheels steering system (4WS) and (f) left and (g) right crab steering system.

of 55°. A specialised fifth-wheel coupling (Fig. 2b) has then exploited to enables an almost complete revolution of the upper platform (i.e. within the range $\pm 175^\circ$) while having the ability to sustain tractors with a mass up to 10 tons. The upper platform has a dimension of $6.42 \times 4.46m$ and it is subdivided into four distinct plates each designed to support an individual tractor wheel/track (Fig. 2c). These plates can be independently shifted vertically (Fig. 2d), allowing for variations up to 300 mm. The feature facilitates changing in the ground configuration, enabling the examination of stability over irregularities such as bumps, potholes, and presence of obstacles. Integrated into each plate, there are four load-cells for the real-time measurement of the forces discharged to the ground by the wheel. In this way, it is possible to monitor the stability state and determine the beginning of a rollover as soon as one of the four forces become zero. In addition, it facilitates the determination of the Centre of Gravity (CoG) location. The tractor is secured to the platform by chains, which are kept loose to prevent interference with the vehicle rollover dynamics (Fig. 2e). Their weight is obviously taken into consideration by measuring system in order to account just the net weight of the machine resting on the rig plates. To ensure the accuracy of experiments and prevent unintended vehicle sliding, special metal grids are used for the platform ground. They are designed with small reliefs that snugly fit into the tire rubber (Fig. 2d). The platform movements are relatively slow as it is designed to perform tests in quasi-static conditions. Indeed, the tractor speeds operating in the mountains are often limited and the dynamic effects are less noticeable.

2.2. Tested tractors

To provide a preliminary view of the stability digital twin approach, together with the potentiality of the rotating-tilting rig, three different models of four-wheel drive tractors commonly used in mountain areas have been tested. All of them have rigid frame configuration with a pivoting front axle, and their general features are shown in Table 1. In detail.

1. New Holland TN-75V (Fig. 4a), a compact orchard-type tractor, thus characterised by a narrow track width such as to allow quick and agile access through the rows of orchards or vineyards; these cultivations are often organised on terraced slope so that the machine

Table 1
Tractor main characteristics.

Properties	Unit	New Holland	New	Reform
		TN-75V	Holland	Metrac H75
			T6.175	
Weight	[kg]	2460	5740	2500
Max. Eng. Rated power	[kW]	55	129	55
Max. Eng. Torque	[Nm]	297	650	300
Steering modes	–	Front steering	Front steering	Front steering Rear steering Crab steering 4-Wheel steering Offset 4-wheel steering
Fuel capacity	[l]	57	218	90
Front tyres	–	280/70R16	480/65R28	394/52R15
Rear tyres	–	360/70R28	600/65R38	394/52R15
Front axle pivoting angle limit	–	5	15	15
Ground clearance	[mm]	240	478	380

moves in safety conditions within the row; manoeuvring to reach the next row, however, can be very dangerous since it is necessary to change height levels (i.e. helix path).

2. New Holland T6.175 (Fig. 4b), a conventional medium/large size tractor often used in forestry activities or at least for the heaviest tasks in mountain farms.
3. Reform Metrac H75 (Fig. 4c), a medium-sized tractor with isodiametric wheels designed to work in high slope environments; it also features an independent steering system in the rear axle which allows both to reduce the turning radius (e.g. 4-wheel steering) and to increase the motion capability (e.g. crab steering, offset 4-wheel steering, etc.). In Fig. 5 all the possible steering configurations are schematised.

2.3. Rollover stability model

The study and simulation of tractor rollover stability behaviour is based on a mathematical model of its kinematics, derived from the work of Previati et al. (Previati et al., 2014). The focus, in particular, shifts to common 4-wheels tractors with a rigid frame and a pivoting front axle. The following hypotheses are assumed: (1) the front axle is symmetric with respect to the position of the pivoting point, (2) the front pivoting axle is frictionless, and (3) the tyre-terrain contact force has direction according to the action of gravity. Ideally, the point of contact between the wheel and the ground is located in the centreline of the tire. Anyhow, in presence of a deformable tire, and as the slope increases, this point tends to move toward the tire outer downstream edge. This, in particular, is true for side rollovers or close to that direction. The reference standards (ISO-16231-2, 2015) assumes that, immediately before the rollover event, the point is in a position close to 75 % of the tire width. In case of longitudinal rollover, the contact point should move forward or backward, but due to the high stiffness of the tire in that direction, the phenomenon can be neglected. The model, to be more accurate, therefore should account for this displacement, which tends to increase the stability of the machine (i.e. tipping occurs at greater angles). However, this involves characterising the tires in terms of elasticity, which in addition to shape and size depends on the material used and its condition as well as inflation pressure. Therefore, in this first version of the model the following additional assumption has been adopted: (4) the

equivalent to having a narrower track). In addition, the model considers (5) a rigid ground surface (i.e., no ground subsidence) as a coefficient of friction such that the machine does not slip. From the point of view of this work, these conditions are not limiting, since the intent is to evaluate the intrinsic stability of the machine regardless of external conditions (except slope). Then, (6) the change in the CoG position due to the displacement of loose mechanical parts (i.e., parts with negligible mass relative to the total one) and the displacement of liquids in tanks (i.e., tanks filled) are considered negligible. Finally, the last hypothesis (7) considers a quasi-static analysis (i.e., dynamic effects are neglected). This particularly simplifies the experimental part, since it is difficult to verify the stability of a machine under dynamic conditions. In any case, tractors normally proceed at low speed during operations, particularly in steep and uneven terrain.

The determination of the tractor rollover stability condition is based on the evaluation of each of the four wheels-ground contact forces: if at least one of these is null or negative, it means that an instability condition is occurring. With reference to Fig. 6, and assuming that all the dimensional characteristics of the tractor are known (e.g. wheelbase, rear and front track, etc.) as well as the position of the CoG, the normal components of the reaction forces acting on the tyres can be computed considering the momentum equilibrium around the axes r_3 , r_2 and r_1 (of the front and rear part separately). This corresponds to solve the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} r_3 : (F_{FL,z} + F_{FR,z}) wb - Mg_x CoG_z + Mg_z CoG_x = 0 \\ r_2 : (F_{RL,z} + F_{RR,z}) wb + Mg_x CoG_z + Mg_z (wb - CoG_x) = 0 \\ r_1 \text{ front} : (F_{RL,z} - F_{RR,z}) \frac{rt}{2} + (F_{RL,y} + F_{RR,y}) hf - Mg_y (CoG_z - hf) + Mg_z CoG_y = 0 \\ r_1 \text{ rear} : (F_{FL,z} - F_{FR,z}) \frac{ft}{2} + (F_{FL,y} + F_{FR,y}) hf = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

tire-ground contact area is a point located in the centre of the tire. For future versions, it is planned to integrate into the model specific procedures to take into account the elastic deformations of the tyres under stress and a more reliable estimate of the points at which the forces acting on each wheel are applied to the ground. In any case, the current solution represents a condition that theoretically provides more restrictive results than the actual rollover limits (i.e. this condition is

where F_{ij} is the j -th component of the contact force of the i -th wheel (i.e. FL: front left, FR: front right, RL: rear left, RR: rear right), wb is the wheelbase, ft the front track, rt the rear track, hf the front axle height, M the tractor mass and CoG the position of the Centre of Gravity. Finally, g_x , g_y and g_z are the gravity vector components referred to the tractor reference system, that can be expressed in function of angles α and β as:

Fig. 6. Rollover stability model.

$$\mathbf{g} = (g_x, g_y, g_z) = g(\sin \alpha \cos \beta, -\sin \alpha \sin \beta, -\cos \alpha) \quad (2)$$

where $g = 9.81 \text{ ms}^{-2}$. As consequence of hypothesis (3), the y -component of the force can be expressed in terms of the normal component as:

$$F_{ij,y} = F_{ij,z} \tan \alpha \sin \beta \quad (3)$$

Substituting equations (2) and (3) into system (1) and solving for the force components, a close solution can be determined. Related details are not reported for lack of space.

This result is used to determine the condition of rollover static stability: given an orientation and configuration of the machine and given an angle of inclination, the machine results unstable if at least one of the tyre contact forces is zero or negative. The rollover limit angle is then sought using an iterative computation based on a successive approximation method.

2.4. Measure of the centre of gravity position

One of the parameters that plays an important role in the stability problem is the position of the CoG within the volume of the tractor. The ISO 16231-2 standard (ISO-16231-2, 2015) considers to evaluate the distribution of the forces acting on each wheel when the tractor is on a horizontal plane and when it is tilted longitudinally. This measurement is done directly by taking advantage of the tilting platform, since it allows both measuring the force of each wheel and tilting the machine. In our stability digital twin approach, exploiting the fact that the platform allows for the easy orientation of the tractor and in order to increase the accuracy, many placements of the machine are considered and thus an average value is preliminarily calculated.

With reference to Fig. 6, the force momentum equilibrium around the three axes r_1 , r_2 and r_4 is considered.

$$\begin{cases} (F_{RL,z} + F_{RR,z}) wb + Mg_x CoG_z + Mg_z (wb - CoG_x) = 0 \\ (F_{FL,z} + F_{FR,z}) wb - Mg_x CoG_z + Mg_z CoG_x = 0 \\ (F_{RL,z} - F_{RR,z}) \frac{rt}{2} + (F_{FL,z} - F_{FR,z}) \frac{ft}{2} - Mg_y CoG_z + Mg_z CoG_y = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Note that since all axes belong to the plane, only the weight force and the contact forces component normal to the planes generate a force momentum. The mass M of the tractor is calculated as the sum of the four force components when the machine is horizontal.

System (4) can be rewritten in matrix form, as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -g_z & 0 & g_x \\ g_z & 0 & -g_x \\ 0 & g_z & -g_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} CoG_x \\ CoG_y \\ CoG_z \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{F_{RL,z} + F_{RR,z}}{M} wb + g_z wb \\ \frac{F_{FL,z} + F_{FR,z}}{M} wb \\ \frac{F_{RL,z} - F_{RR,z}}{M} \frac{rt}{2} + \frac{F_{FL,z} - F_{FR,z}}{M} \frac{ft}{2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

This represents the equilibrium in a single orientation of the machine. Further equations can be therefore added to the system as the configurations number increases. Therefore:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -g_{z,1} & 0 & g_{x,1} \\ g_{z,1} & 0 & -g_{x,1} \\ 0 & g_{z,1} & -g_{y,1} \\ -g_{z,2} & 0 & g_{x,2} \\ g_{z,2} & 0 & -g_{x,2} \\ 0 & g_{z,2} & -g_{y,2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} CoG_x \\ CoG_y \\ CoG_z \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{F_{RL,z,1} + F_{RR,z,1}}{M} wb + g_{z,1} wb \\ \frac{F_{FL,z,1} + F_{FR,z,1}}{M} wb \\ \frac{F_{RL,z,1} - F_{RR,z,1}}{M} \frac{rt}{2} + \frac{F_{FL,z,1} - F_{FR,z,1}}{M} \frac{ft}{2} \\ \frac{F_{RL,z,2} + F_{RR,z,2}}{M} wb + g_{z,2} wb \\ \frac{F_{FL,z,2} + F_{FR,z,2}}{M} wb \\ \frac{F_{RL,z,2} - F_{RR,z,2}}{M} \frac{rt}{2} + \frac{F_{FL,z,2} - F_{FR,z,2}}{M} \frac{ft}{2} \\ \dots \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

That represents a linear system in the form $\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}$. The solution, i.e. the position of the CoG, is determined as $\mathbf{x} = \text{inv}(\mathbf{A})\mathbf{b}$. Since \mathbf{A} is a non-square matrix (i.e. 3 columns and a number of rows equal to the number of tests considered, >3), its pseudo-inverse (i.e. $\text{inv}(\mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{A}^+$) must be considered.

2.5. Rollover stability test

The rollover tests (Fig. 7) have been conducted on all the considered tractors exploiting the test rig previously described, and under consistent conditions with full fuel tanks and tire pressures adjusted to the nominal value. The initial phase of the measurement procedure involved the determination of the characteristic dimensions (e.g. wheelbase, track, etc.) using a tape measure. The platform has been then positioned horizontally for the tare of the four plates. After this, the tractor under test has loaded for the CoG position determination.

The securing of the machine involved the use of chains, which have not been tightened to prevent any influence on the measurement. The test for locating the CoG involved tilting the platform at different values avoiding the rollover of the machine (i.e. 15° and 20°) and orientating the tractor in different positions throughout the full circular angle with step of 15° . At each step, the weight distribution on the four wheels is then measured and used to solve system (6). This approach helps mitigate measurement errors resulting from factors such as the displacement of the liquid in the tank and tyre deformation with the slope. In the subsequent phase of the stability analysis, the front wheels have been securely fixed with tight chains, whereas the rear wheels employ slightly loose chains enabling the wheels to detach from the platform and thus facilitating a controlled partial rollover. This has no influence on the measure as in most of the conditions (except for $|\beta| > 150^\circ$) the rear axle

Fig. 7. Static rollover test: (a) New Holland TN-75V, (b) New Holland T6.175 and (c) Reform Metrac H75.

detaches first, and the tractor begins to tip over by rotating around the pivoting front axle. This guarantees that the tractor does not move during and after the test, as well as greater safety. The rollover stability test involved the positioning of the tractor at various orientations (i.e. in general from -180° to 180°) with steps of 15° , even if for inclinations close to the longitudinal one the tests are not practicable due to unavoidable machine slipping. For each configuration, the plane has been tilted until instability occurred, represented by the detachment of at least one tire from the surface. To ensure statistical robustness and accuracy of the results, the same test has been repeated three times for each orientation of the machine.

The tractors have also been tested under different steering conditions, which can be very complex as in the case of the mountain-specialist machine, that permits different steering configurations (i.e. four-wheel steering, crab steering, etc.). In fact, stability can be roughly assessed by considering the extent of the baseline area, i.e. the area that in the case of a rigid-frame tractor connects the four-wheel contact points. As soon as the projection of the CoG leaves this area due to the change in slope, instability occurs. In the case of tractors with a pivoting front axle, the base area consists of a triangle with two vertices at the rear contact points and the third at the pivot joint (Fig. 8). Since the axis of rotation of each wheel defining the steering angle does not intersect with the respective contact point, there is a displacement in the contact itself. This leads to a deformation of the stability baseline as demonstrate in Fig. 8. Theoretically, front steering should have no effect on stability due to the presence of the pivoting axle.

2.6. Stability map

One of the main outcomes of this digital twin approach is the generation of stability maps (Fig. 9), achieved by combining both modelling and experimental measurements, which comprehensively characterise the behaviour of machines on inclined surfaces. A stability map consists of a polar diagram in which: (1) the angular coordinate represents the orientation β of the slope with respect to the tractor longitudinal axis (i.e. orientation axis). For example, $\beta = +90^\circ$ indicates a lateral slope with valley bottom to the right, while $\beta = -90^\circ$ with valley bottom to the left; $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\pm 180^\circ$ means that the tractor is ascending and descending, respectively, moving in the direction of the slope. Three regions can be identified, namely extended lateral left/right rollover areas (i.e. blue and red areas, respectively, in Fig. 9) and extended longitudinal rollover area (i.e. grey area). (2) The radial coordinate represents the instability tilting angle α_{lim} (i.e. tilting axis), beyond which rollover occurs. In particular, the figures display a continuous line, with a characteristic iron shape, representing the output of the mathematical model, and markers indicating experimental measurements under different conditions. Currently, tests on real tractors are only possible in the extended left and right lateral rollover regions. Beyond these limits the machine starts to slip due to the increased rejection to rollover and also the safety chains start to affect the measurement.

3. Results

The first results and objectives of this work are the measure of the tractor mass, its distribution between the front and rear axles, and the

Fig. 8. Steer influence on rollover stability.

Fig. 9. Example of a stability map.

Table 2

Measured properties of the tractors tested. Note that only the level of the fuel tank has been taken into account, as all other tanks (e.g., hydraulic oil, brake oil, engine oil, AdBlue, etc.) have been considered to be of lower volume; in any case, their level must always be above a certain minimum to ensure proper operation of the machine.

	Unit	New Holland TN-75V	New Holland T6.175	Reform Metrac H75
Wheelbase	[mm]	2060	2642	2150
Rear track	[mm]	860	1685	1740
Front track	[mm]	940	1804	1740
Tyre pressure	[kPa]	125	160	170 ^(rear) – 120 ^(front)
Fuel tank level	–	Full	Full	Full
Ballast	[kg]	No	No	No
Mass	–	2303	6506	2852
Mass distribution	[% _f – % _r]	39–61	44–56	43–57
CoG position (x, y, z)	[mm]	(805, –11, 676)	(1166, –18, 984)	(936, –84, 675)

CoG position. Table 2 shows the values obtained for the machines under study. Notably, all three tractors exhibit a predominant weight distribution on the rear axle, approximately 60 %, which is a characteristic feature of the front pivoting axle architecture. A comparative analysis between the “orchard” tractor and the mountain-specialist one reveals identical CoG heights. Nevertheless, in the latter case, the significantly wider base area (almost double) contributes to enhanced stability.

The second, and main, outcome of the digital twin approach is the generation of the stability maps visible in Figs. 10–12. The figures report both the output of the mathematical model, and markers indicating experimental measurements under different steering conditions. The theoretical model is generally consistent with experimental observations but, in many conditions, there is not an exact overlap between the two. As mentioned in the previous sections and as visible from the figures, the experimental tests were performed only for the extended lateral

Fig. 10. New Holland TN-75V stability map.

Fig. 11. New Holland T6.175, stability map.

Fig. 12. Reform Metrac H75, stability map.

orientation (i.e., in general within the range $\pm 45^\circ$ from the lateral orientation, but depending on the specific machine and tyres). Outside this region, in fact, the stability angle is high and results in machine

sliding, thus invalidating the test. In the future, to solve or at least limit this problem, blocks will be placed against the bead of the wheels, as also specified by ISO and SAE standards (i.e., ISO 16333:2011 and SAE J2180_201105). As this may affect the measurement, the standard (ISO 16333:2011, 2011) sets a maximum height limit for the block (i.e. 60 mm or 2/3 of the bead height). In any case, they will only be used in the most critical conditions, where it is currently not possible to take measurements. In the case of the orchard tractor (Fig. 10), a lower instability angle is always predicted, anyhow resulting in favour of safety. This does not verify for the New Holland T6.175 (Fig. 11), where there are regions of both underestimation and overestimation of the stability limit, with the crossing occurring near the lateral rollover area. A non-perfect overlap is also observed for the Reform Metrac H75 (Fig. 12), where also a different effect and variability emerge between tipping towards the cab side (i.e. left) and the engine side (i.e. right).

To visualise and quantify the error of the model compared to real measurements, Figs. 13–15 show the measured instability angles plotted against the simulated values, belonging to the same tractor orientation. Ideally, a model without error would have all points aligned along the 45° line (dashed line in the figures). Error bands are also included in the graph to provide an indication of the model accuracy. Note that although the graphs only report the tilting angle α on both the x and y axes, this angle is correlated with the machine orientation β : lower α values are associated with lateral rollovers, while higher values correspond to longitudinal rollovers. As shown in the figures, the error generally falls within a 10 % margin, with outliers reaching up to 20 %, especially in conditions closer to longitudinal rollover. A more detailed quantification of the model error is provided in Table 3, where the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value of the stability model, compared to the experimental data (considered as observed values), are reported. The results show a fairly good correlation for the New Holland T6-175 and the Reform Metrac H75. However, the first tested tractor exhibits greater uncertainty, with RMSE values reaching up to 4° , while the other machines show RMSE values around 2° . Considering that a theoretical model always has a certain degree of uncertainty, especially in this application, it is important to determine whether this error is pro-safety or if leads to a non-safety response and whether it ensures minimal error under the most critical. To further investigate this aspect, Figs. 13–15 also report the linear regression line fitting the error model (solid line).

This is exploited to determine the behaviour of the error, reporting the deviation of the model predictions from the experimental data. It is thus a further indicator of the goodness of the model considered, making it possible to identify the range of validity and the crossover point between a pro-safety and a non-safety response, as well as whether the deviation can be considered constant. This offset represents a possible corrective parameter to adjust the behaviour of the model (i.e. the model can be adapted and thus give satisfactory results without having to increase its complexity). As visible in Table 4, the linear regression model fits well the experimental vs. simulated data system. This is in particular confirmed by both from the high R^2 values, although in some the value is smaller (i.e. around 0.7 in the case of New Holland T6.175), and from the slope p-values lower than 0.05, which denote high statistical significance of the data set. The regression model slope is generally close to 1 (i.e. model and experimental data overlapping) but always >1 . This implies that, depending on the value of the intercept, the model will return overestimated results (for high tilt angles) or underestimated results (for smaller tilt angles). With regard to the intercept, the regression model predicts the null hypothesis (i.e. p-value >0.05) only in certain cases. This indicates that there is always an offset between simulated and experimental data. However, considering the real range of interest, i.e. considering that the tipping angles in tractors are generally between 25° and 55° , it can be seen how the response of the model becomes dependent on the tractor type considered. In the case of the New Holland TN-75V (Fig. 13), the linear regression model is always above the reference line, so that the model (and the model parameters

Fig. 13. New Holland TN-75V, error between experimental data and model: (a) left, (b) straight and (c) right steering directions. The graphs report also the error bands and the linear model fit line (statistical values of the linear model fit are reported in Table 4).

Fig. 14. New Holland T6.175, error between experimental data and model: (a) left, (b) straight and (c) right steering directions. The graphs report also the error bands and the linear model fit line (statistical values of the linear model fit are reported in Table 4).

considered) are always in favour of safety. In the case of the New Holland T6.175 and the Reform Metrac H75, instead the model results fall within the error bands of $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 5\%$, respectively.

Experimental trials involved testing machines with various steering orientations and configurations. The impact of front-wheel steering is practically negligible. This is evident in Figs. 10 and 11 as the stability baseline forms a triangle that closes with a vertex at the front axle joint, the position of which is independent of the steering angle. Contrastingly, when the rear axle is steered, a distinct influence is observed. Specifically, with respect to the Reform Metrac tractor (Fig. 12): (1) orienting the rear wheels downstream (i.e. steering upstream in the case of four wheels steering, or downstream lateral movement in the case of crab steering) leads to a reduction in stability. (2) Conversely, moving the rear wheels upstream has the opposite effect, enhancing stability.

4. Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to assess and validate the feasibility of conducting experimental rollover tests across various machine orientations. This approach marks a significant advancement, as existing literature predominantly focuses on purely lateral or, less frequently, longitudinal tilting, leaving out all the intermediate configurations. This limitation is primarily due to the challenges associated with long preparation times and safety concerns. For example, studies such as Franceschetti et al. (2021) and Majdan et al. (2021), are limited only to lateral rollover evaluation, while Pessina et al. (2022) examines

different orientations but only to few cases due to the time-consuming preparation. In contrast, Carabin et al. (2016); Jang et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2014, 2018) explore more complex scenarios but rely on scaled models. While these models are carefully designed and calibrated, they cannot fully account for all real-world factors. The new experimental system overcomes these limitations by enabling safe and relatively rapid measurements on full-scale machines. With a single tractor setup, it is possible to easily perform both CoG position measurements and extensive rollover tests across different machine orientations.

A secondary aim was to evaluate the effectiveness of a stability model in predicting tractor stability performance. Despite some discrepancies between the model and the experimental data, the results are more than acceptable considering the nature of the simplified model. Indeed, in this context, “simplified” refers to a model that requires minimal computational resources, enabling rapid results (i.e. an essential requirement for integration into mechatronic warning systems) and avoids reliance on parameters that are not quickly or difficult to quantify. In this way the model is more easily adaptable to many situations (e.g. it can be calibrated to provide more accurate results under the most critical conditions, and subsequently larger safety factors can be considered in other situations).

In any case, to obtain a more truthful response the interaction between the wheel and the ground and therefore tyre deformations have to be taken into account. Indeed, this results in both a displacement in the tyre-terrain contact point (i.e. it moves toward the lower tire edge) and an alteration in the orientation of the machine with respect to the

Fig. 15. New Holland T6.175, error between experimental data and model: (a) left, (b) straight and (c) right four-wheel steering directions; (d) left and (e) right crab steering directions. The graphs report also the error bands and the linear model fit line (statistical values of the linear model fit are reported in Table 4).

Table 3

Statistical comparison between the stability model prediction and experimental data.

Tractor model	Steering direction	Fig.	R ²	RMSE [°]
New holland TN-75V	Straight	11b	0.688	3.31
	Left	11a	0.397	4.28
	Right	11c	0.466	3.94
New holland T6.175	Straight	13a	0.808	3.52
	Left	13b	0.706	2.32
	Right	13c	0.641	2.35
Reform metrac H75	Straight	15b	0.871	2.67
	4WS - left	15a	0.901	2.30
	4WS - right	15c	0.919	1.66
	Crab - left	15d	0.944	1.33
	Crab - right	15e	0.865	2.85

ground reference plane. This explains, for instance, the different behaviour between the New Holland TN-75V, where the model is always in favour of safety, and the New Holland T6.175 where this is not always the case. With the former tractor in fact, due to the narrower track width, the rollover occurs at lower angles. This, however, results in less lateral tyre loading and therefore also less deformation. In the second case, on the other hand, the lateral deformation is greater and thus also the relative displacement between the contact point and CoG position (i. e. the distance between CoG and outer point is reduced). The consequence is a reduction of the stability angle compared to the simulated one.

In addition, this discrepancy is different between conditions with and without steered wheels, with greater variations in the former case. This is due to a phenomenon, not yet integrated into the model, related to the non-zero (usually positive) camber angle of the front wheels: this causes

the front of the vehicle to rise as the steering angle increases. The stored potential energy is used then to generate a self-aligning torque at the wheels that steers them to the central position (by releasing the steering and moving forward with the vehicle). However, the raising of the front also causes a shift of the CoG position, as shown in Fig. 16a: the position rises and falls back towards the rear. The first contribution tends to reduce the rollover stability angle, but is overwhelmed by the second movement, which instead increases it. The magnitude of this second contribution, however, depends on the orientation of the tractor, as shown in Fig. 16b, being more favourable with the tractor moving up the slope.

Notably, the condition of maximum instability is observed close to lateral tipping, but not precisely at that point. Contrary to current safety regulation (ISO-16231-2, 2015), the highest risk occurs when the operator traverses a slope laterally with a slightly downward trajectory (up to 20° to the transverse). For example, in the case of the New Holland TN-75V (Fig. 10) the limit rollover angle decreases from 31.3° in lateral rollover to 29.6° when β = 70°.

Finally, Fig. 17 illustrates the simulated behaviours of the three tractor types collectively. It is noteworthy that despite the variations in machine weight, stability relies only on geometric factors. The orchard tractor, with its narrow track width, exhibits a limited stability region compared to the mountain-specialist tractor, where the track width is instead maximised. In the latter case, an asymmetrical feature arises due to the side-by-side positioning of the cab and engine; for instance, the Metrac, when tilted to the left, can reach angles exceeding 50°, while tilting to the right stops at a still excellent 42°. The architecture of its structure aims to lower the centre of gravity as much as possible.

These considerations and the digital-twin approach presented demonstrate the importance of experimental validation of the implemented models - a factor that is often overlooked or only partially

Table 4

Statistical values of the error linear model fit. In p-value the following notation is considered: (○) statistically highly significant, (●●) statistically significant, (●●●) statistically not significant. Note that R^2 refers to the coefficient of determination of the linear model used to fit the error.

Tractor model	Steering direction	Fig.	Intercept			Slope			R^2
			Value	SE	p-value	Value	SE	p-value	
New holland TN-75V	Straight	11b	-0.28	2.253	0.900 (●●●)	1.097	0.076	$1e^{-16}$ (○)	0.848
	Left	11a	-6.52	3.237	0.060 (●●)	1.376	0.115	$2e^{-9}$ (○)	0.899
	Right	11c	-10.2	4.763	0.048 (●●)	1.482	0.170	$2e^{-7}$ (○)	0.826
New holland T6.175	Straight	13a	-17.5	2.379	$5e^{-9}$ (○)	1.499	0.062	$2e^{-25}$ (○)	0.935
	Left	13b	-11.9	4.729	0.017 (●●)	1.330	0.131	$7e^{-12}$ (○)	0.752
	Right	13c	-5.82	4.839	0.238 (●●●)	1.139	0.134	$6e^{-10}$ (○)	0.680
Reform metrac H75	Straight	15b	-15.2	2.414	$5e^{-7}$ (○)	1.358	0.053	$2e^{-22}$ (○)	0.955
	4WS - left	15a	-15.2	1.643	$5e^{-9}$ (○)	1.368	0.037	$3e^{-21}$ (○)	0.984
	4WS - right	15c	-8.41	2.489	0.002 (●●)	1.182	0.056	$2e^{-17}$ (○)	0.946
	Crab - left	15d	-0.50	1.448	0.733 (●●●)	1.032	0.032	$2e^{-25}$ (○)	0.972
	Crab - right	15e	-19.2	2.732	$7e^{-8}$ (○)	1.420	0.060	$2e^{-21}$ (○)	0.948

Fig. 16. Influence of camber angle on rollover stability angle: (a) CoG position shift with wheel steering, (b) effect on rollover stability angle for different machine orientations.

Fig. 17. Stability maps comparison.

considered, as seen, for example, in Baker and Guzzomi (2013); Mazetto et al. (2013) and Previati et al. (2014).

5. Conclusions

In this work, a newly stability digital twin approach has been applied to three different tractors to study their (static) rollover stability behaviour in presence of slopes. The approach, that could potentially extend conventional rollover certification tests, integrates modelling procedures with actual measurements obtained from a rotating and tiltable test rig to assess risks under various operational conditions. Results are presented in a final stability map (a polar diagram) that identifies different risk levels for rollover accidents. The tests on the selected tractors confirmed the tool’s effectiveness, particularly for the preliminary detection of the centre of gravity (CoG) position (i.e. essential for calibrating theoretical models) and for the (quick) measurements of the rollover angles in different operations conditions.

Regarding the specific results obtained with the tractors studied, the

stability maps have quantitatively highlighted the objectively greater safety that can be achieved with specialised mountain tractors. Their use should be more highly recommended in all hilly and mountainous areas, as they can guarantee lateral tilt stability up to slopes of up to 120 %. The weak points of these machines, however, are: (a) the asymmetry of the rollover limits, which is still a remarkable 84 % when the cab side is considered; (b) the purchase costs, which are on average 20–25 % higher than for conventional tractors.

Considering the correspondence between simulated and measured tipping angles in different directions, the model provides more than acceptable results considering its nature of simplicity. In general, it tends to slightly overestimate stability in the case of near-side overturning. In other conditions, however, it provides results not always in favour of safety. In any case, it must be remarked that in this study the model is deliberately kept simple and dependent on a few easily measurable and/or quantifiable parameters (e.g. tractor characteristics dimensions and CoG position). This makes it suitable both for providing an initial quick estimate of machine stability behaviour and possibly for integration into rollover safety systems without the need of actively monitoring many parameters (i.e. only the tractor orientation is required). In this regard, different model tuning parameters can always be adapted (i.e. exploiting the experimental test) depending on the areas of operation. Nevertheless, significant opportunities for improvement exist in the simulator both with regard to tractor kinematics (e.g. steering influence) but particularly with regard to the modelling of tyres as elastic bodies. Indeed, elasticity causes a displacement of the wheel-ground contact point with respect to the position of the CoG and an alteration in the orientation of the machine with respect to the ground reference plane. The main problem with this approach is the experimental determination of the elastic behaviour of tyres: it is influenced by numerous factors, including the shape and material of the tyre, the direction of load application and the inflation pressure. In addition, once calibrated through static rollover experimental tests, the model can be exploited for complex dynamic simulations in common operating scenarios, taking into account, for example, different asperities and road profiles, machine speeds and trajectories.

The development of stability maps, achieved through the

characterisation of various machines under different operational contexts and with different implements attached, can be exploited for real-time monitoring of machine stability conditions. This is both by alerting the operator in the event of approaching dangerous conditions and a posteriori by analysing and possibly modifying the path normally followed by the tractor within the field/orchard to ensure greater safety. Furthermore, the stability map logic of the digital twin approach has the potential to improve the current certification procedure or, at the very least, enhance and validate future certification methodologies based on simulations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giovanni Carabin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Merve Karaca:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Fabrizio Mazzetto:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Science4Impact statement

The scientific results of this work and the line of study considered could contribute to improving tractor operator safety against rollover. This could be achieved through two approaches: (1) by contributing to the improvement of certification testing standards and methodologies for machines (and their equipment). (2) The twin-model approach and the new experimental test rig make it easy to test different machines in different configurations (possibly equipped with different implements) and under different operating scenarios. These data, in forms of stability maps, can be exploited to study new, more targeted safety systems, or otherwise improve existing ones.

Nomenclature

Symbol	Description	unit
α	Tilting angle	[°]
β	Tractor orientation angle with respect to the main slope line	[°]
CoG	Centre of gravity	–
CoG_i	CoG position i-th (i.e. $i = x, y, z$) component	[mm]
ft	Front track	[mm]
F_{RLi}	Rear-left wheel contact force i-th (i.e. $i = x, y, z$) component	[N]
F_{FLi}	Front-left wheel contact force i-th (i.e. $i = x, y, z$) component	[N]
F_{FRi}	Front-right wheel contact force i-th (i.e. $i = x, y, z$) component	[N]
F_{RRi}	Rear-right wheel contact force i-th (i.e. $i = x, y, z$) component	[N]
g	Earth gravitational acceleration constant	[m s ⁻²]
hr	Rear axle height	[mm]
hf	Front axle height	[mm]
M	Tractor mass	[kg]
rt	Rear track	[mm]
wb	Wheelbase	[mm]

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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